

The Research Design on the Management of Students' English Learning Assessment Activities at High Schools in Tien Giang Province, Vietnam

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ABSTRACT: This paper investigates the research design on the management of students' English learning assessment activities at high schools in the approach of PDCA (*Plan, Do, Check, Act*). It employed Kumar's (2011) eight-step format in designing the research process and manipulated Taro's (1973) formula to calculate its sample size. The sampling for two groups of administrators, teachers of English and students was randomly taken from 10 out of 38 high schools in Tien Giang province, Vietnam. As a result, there were 418 educators and 1829 students chosen, which was much higher than its required sample sizes of 213 administrators, teachers and 397 learners in two groups. Besides, the study exploited a mixed research method to effectively collect quantitative data through questionnaires and qualitative ones through in-depth interviews. Additionally, the study applied SPSS 27.0 software for calculating exploratory factor analysis (EFA), total variance explained and Cronbach's alpha, and then compared them with three accepted values of 0.3, 50.0% and 0.7, accordingly, for confirming their connection and reliability within each group. The findings indicate that all items in questionnaires met the requirements in this research.

KEYWORDS: High school, management of English learning assessment activities, research design, research process, reliability, PDCA

INTRODUCTION

A research design is an overall plan that plays a pivotal role in bridging theory and practice, systematically guiding the research process (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). It reflects the researcher's mindset, demonstrating the selection of the most suitable methodology to address the research questions (Asenahabi, 2019). According to Wisenthige (2023), it is a methodological framework, a collection of techniques chosen by the researcher to conduct their work scientifically. It serves as a structure ensuring logical consistency throughout the data collection and analysis phases. The research design acts as the "glue" that links the various elements of the study into a unity, aiming to provide reliable answers to the research problem. A well-designed study is the foundation for ensuring the accuracy, reliability and validity of the research findings. Therefore, a research design is a decisive factor in the success of any academic work.

Gupta (2023) posits that a research design, which includes a conceptual framework and strategy, logically connects the study's components. It guides the process of collecting objective data to test hypotheses. It also serves as a blueprint, directing the planning, implementation and analysis, helping the researcher select appropriate methods to solve the problem. According to Wisenthige (2023), a successful research design provides accurate and objective insights. It is a key factor in ensuring the reliability and validity of the results, contributing to the development of scientific knowledge and acting as a guiding compass for the entire research process.

Additionally, a research design incorporates a strategy for interpreting data, thereby leading to valid conclusions and recommendations (Saliya, 2023). Researchers consider it a detailed plan for collecting, measuring, and analyzing data. It helps them make crucial decisions about what, where, how much and when to conduct the study, and how to conduct the steps. A good research design usually has a clear structure, ensuring the study's success and effectively addressing the problem. It is a pivotal element that determines the scientific value of the research. It guides the entire process, from data collection to final conclusions. Asenahabi (2019, p. 87) states that "the essence of research design is to achieve the research objectives clearly, objectively, accurately and economically, controlling external changes and minimizing errors." The research design in this study mainly focuses the following questions:

- (1) How is the research process designed in this study?

- (2) How is the research design conducted?
- (3) Are the research items reliable for implementing this study or not?

RESEARCH PROCESS

A research process is a series of closely linked steps that requires the researcher to select appropriate methods, procedures and techniques to achieve the research objectives (Kothari, 2004; Kumar, 2011; Thomas, 2021). To succeed in conducting a study, a deep understanding of research methods is crucial. The main steps in the research process, according to Thomas (2021), include "identifying the problem, reviewing the literature, developing objectives, selecting a research design, constructing a proposal, seeking approval, conducting the research, collecting and analyzing data, interpreting the results, preparing a report/dissertation, presenting the results and publishing" (p. 30). These steps are not necessarily linear but can be intertwined, requiring the researcher to be flexible and adaptable. Mastering this process is the foundation for conducting valuable scientific research.

In the scope of this study, Kumar's (2011) research process is employed with eight basic steps.

Step 1: *Clearly identify the research problem.* This is a critical step that helps the researcher select the objectives and methods of the study appropriately (Kumar, 2011; Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Mukherjee, 2020). The more specific and clear the research problem is, the more effective the design, measurement procedures, sampling strategy, data analysis and presentation style will become. Therefore, the researcher needs to carefully consider the problem and evaluate its feasibility based on personal and supervisory resources regarding finance, time and expertise. Identifying knowledge gaps related to statistics, data analysis and interpretation also plays a vital role, helping the researcher prepare thoroughly. Identifying the research problem is not only the starting point but also the foundation that determines the success of the entire research process, helping minimize risks and unexpected impacts during implementation. The research problem in this study is *'The Management of students' English Learning Assessment Activities at High Schools in Tien Giang Province'*.

Step 2: *Conceptualize the research design.* Scientific research requires the use of appropriate methodology to explore, describe and explain phenomena systematically, controllably and rigorously. It not only seeks unknown things but also identifies relationships, causes to test and correct previous errors (Kumar, 2011). Especially, its results depend on the methods used to answer the research questions. The research design includes measurement procedures, sampling strategies, an analytical framework, and a timeline (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Choosing a suitable research design is crucial to ensure the reliability of the results. Therefore, the selection of a research design must be based on its validity and feasibility. Thus, the researcher needs to be familiar with different research designs and choose the one that best suits their research objectives.

In this study, the research issue *'The management of students' English learning assessment activities at high schools in Tien Giang province'* is conducted through the PDCA (Plan, Do, Check, Act) approach. Based on this orientation, the researcher builds a theoretical framework including concepts of English learning assessment, management, and the management of assessment activities. It also covers the steps of *'Plan, Do, Check, and Act'* for managing English learning assessment and identifies factors impacting the management of these assessment activities at high schools.

Step 3: *Develop data collection tools.* In scientific research, a research tool is an instrument used to collect information. It includes observation forms, interview schedules, questionnaires, and interview guides (Saris & Gallhofer, 2014; Pruzan, 2016). Developing research tools is the first practical step in the research process. To collect data effectively, the researcher needs to decide on the appropriate data collection method and then build or select a suitable tool. If using primary data, the researcher needs to design their own tools. If using secondary data, the researcher needs to identify the necessary information and design a data extraction form (Kumar, 2011). To ensure the effectiveness and reliability of the research tools, the researcher should conduct an experimental test of the research tool. The proper selection and design of research tools are crucial for ensuring the quality of the collected data and minimizing biases caused by the tools.

In this study, the author used several research tools as the following:

(a) Quantitative data collection tools include a questionnaire for school administrators and teachers and the other one for students to gather information about students' English learning assessment activities, the management of these activities and factors impacting them at high schools in Tien Giang province. To ensure the reliability of the questionnaires, the author constructed and revised them by collecting the opinions of experts, administrators, teachers, and students on the clarity and comprehensibility of the

questions. Ambiguous questions were eliminated, just keeping those with their Cronbach's alpha values from 0.6 or higher and an item-total correlation ones from 0.3 or higher (Cristobal et al., 2007; Hair et al., 2019) before the official survey.

(b) Qualitative data collection tools are in-depth interview questionnaires for school administrators, teachers and students as well as expert opinion surveys for administrators and teachers on the management of students' English learning assessment at high schools in Tien Giang province, providing qualitative information to supplement and clarify the survey issues and the piloting phase.

(c) Data collection tools for educational products are carried out through the review of schools' educational plans, groups' educational plans, teachers' educational plans, lesson plans (pedagogical plans), test questions and answer keys/marking guides, student papers, their learning results, and records of borrowing and returning books/reference materials and teaching equipment for English at the equipment room and library as well as self-made teaching aids by teachers and students for teaching, learning and assessment.

(d) Information collection tools on Party and State policies for foreign languages are implemented through a review of Party resolutions, Prime Minister's directives and decisions, Ministry of Education and Training's circulars, and guiding documents from the Tien Giang Service of Education and Training, school leaders on assessment activities and the management of students' English learning assessment.

(e) Document collection tools for building the theoretical framework are conducted through a review of materials such as monographs, articles, proceedings and papers by experts on the management of students' learning assessment, both in printed and electronic formats.

Step 4: Select the research sample. The accuracy of research results heavily depends on the sampling method. The main goal of sampling is to minimize the difference between the values obtained from the sample and the true values of the population within the constraints of available resources. The fundamental principle of sampling is that if sample units are selected representatively, they can provide a reasonably accurate reflection of the research population with high confidence (Kumar, 2011). When selecting a sample, it is important to avoid bias and achieve maximum accuracy with available resources. There are three main types of sampling designs: random (probability), non-random (non-probability), and mixed (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Thomas, 2021). Each type has various sampling strategies. The researcher needs to be familiar with these designs, understand their advantages and disadvantages, and know their application contexts to choose the most suitable method. The choice of sampling strategy affects the generalizability of the research findings and the type of statistical accreditations used (Kumar, 2011). Therefore, sample selection plays a crucial role in ensuring the validity and reliability of the research.

In this study, the research sample was chosen by using random cluster sampling, which is suitable for the geographical conditions of Tien Giang province. To select the sample, high schools were grouped into five different clusters, with each cluster consisting of two districts or one district with a neighboring city/town, to ensure that the sample was representative of each cluster participation. The number of participants was the percentage of students in each cluster. In this study, there were 10 out of 38 schools randomly selected (two schools per cluster) for the survey, with a total student population of about 15,000 in these 10 schools.

Step 5: Write the research proposal. After completing the preparatory steps, the information will be synthesized into a detailed plan on the research idea and sent to supervisors. This plan's main function is to detail the activities that will be conducted to answer the research questions. The research proposal helps persuade readers about the validity of the methodology, thereby leading to accurate and objective results. An effective research proposal has to clearly state the research objectives, the methods to be used, and the reasons for choosing those methods (Kumar, 2011). A research proposal concisely presents the core issues, highlighting the study's features by providing detailed information on the research topic (Hossain et al., 2022, p. 266).

The research objectives in this study are: (1) to understand the current state of the management of students' English learning assessment at high schools in Tien Giang province and to identify the difficulties in managing these assessment activities; (2) to propose some management solutions based on the PDCA approach to enhance the effectiveness of managing these assessment activities, thereby accurately assessing student competence, meeting the required knowledge and skill, and improving the quality of English teaching and learning at high schools in Tien Giang province.

Some methods used in this study include: a literature review, a questionnaire-based survey, in-depth interviews, learning product analysis, a pilot study, and data processing methods. These methods are appropriate for the nature of the research and help to collect the necessary information to answer the research problems in this study.

Step 6: Collect data. The researcher used appropriate methods to gather information. Depending on the research design, research activities may include interviews, questionnaires, and/or observations. Data collection must adhere to ethical principles to ensure objectivity and respect for the research subjects, especially "adhering to accepted standards of conduct" in practice (Mukherjee, 2020, p. 73; Kapoor, 2021, p. 56). This phase is crucial for providing empirical information to draw valid inferences and conclusions for the research. "It is particularly important that the data collection is directly linked to the research questions the researcher wants to answer" (Creswell & Báez, 2021, p. 107).

In this study, the survey used both paper-based and Google-Form-based questionnaires, which were sent to school administrators, teachers of English and students. The paper-based questionnaires were collected after a week. For the in-depth interview, questionnaires were sent to administrators and teachers seven days before the interview was conducted to help them understand and answer the questions thoroughly. Additionally, official documents from the Ministry/ Tien Giang Service of Education and Training, the annual plans and reports from the schools were also reviewed. The author sought permission from the teaching group to review teaching records, teachers' lesson plans, and annual reports on borrowing and returning teaching equipment and materials at the equipment room and library. The survey and interview period was conducted according to the recommendation letter from Tien Giang Service of Education and Training.

Step 7: Process and present data. Processing data involves organizing and calculating data, including various types of information (descriptive, quantitative, qualitative), and interpreting the results (Cohen et al., 2007, pp. 183-184). The researcher considers appropriate computer software for qualitative and quantitative data analysis. For descriptive research, the researcher may use field-trip notes and content analysis. Quantitative research requires to use the appropriate type of analysis such as frequency, percentages, standard deviation, exploratory factor analysis, Pearson's linear correlation analysis, and regression analysis (Sharma, 2021), and how to present the results logically. Additionally, the researcher needs to identify the variables used in the statistical analysis. The selection of an appropriate analysis method ensures the accuracy and validity of the research findings, helping convey information effectively. The researcher must have a deep understanding of these analytical methods to make the best decisions.

This study uses SPSS 27.0 software for statistical analysis. It performs descriptive statistics for independent variables concerning perceptions of administrators, teachers, and students about the importance and role of students' English learning assessment activities and the management of these activities at high schools. For dependent variables, the study uses exploratory factor analysis, t-tests, Pearson's linear correlation analysis, linear regression analysis to see their correlations. Especially, Cronbach's alpha of items is also used to examine the reliability among variables.

Step 8: Write the report. Writing the report is the final and most challenging step in the research process. The report presents the issues that were explored and draws a conclusion from the findings. The report is written in an academic style with a clear structure and divided into sections/chapters based on the main topics of the study. It fully reflects the process, the findings, and the conclusion drawn in a logical and coherent manner while ensuring objectivity and scientific rigor. The report plays a crucial role in disseminating new findings to the academic community.

RESEARCH DESIGNS

Research instruments

Research instruments are an indispensable component for collecting qualitative and quantitative information. The most common instruments in a research are interviews and questionnaires. According to Cohen et al. (2007) and Sreejesh et al. (2014), a questionnaire is a set of questions asked respondents appropriate instructions. Questionnaires are used in many research fields, including education for surveys and experimental designs. A questionnaire has four functions: it allows collecting data from respondents, provides structure for interviews, offers a standardized means of recording responses, and facilitates the processing of collected data.

In this study, two primary survey instruments are used to collect quantitative and qualitative data. The first one is the questionnaire to gather information from administrators, teachers, and students on the management of students' English learning assessment activities. The second one is the in-depth interview to collect information from experts, administrators and teachers about the current state and effectiveness of some proposed solutions/measures for managing these activities at high schools in Tien Giang province.

The study uses these two instruments because, according to Cohen et al. (2007) and Creswell and Creswell (2018), they can be used to collect large amounts of data at once, saving time, effort, and cost; represent a broad target population; provide descriptive, inferential, and explanatory information; deal with key factors and variables to infer frequencies; collect standardized information (using the same instrument and questions for all participants); identify correlations between variables; support or refute hypotheses about the target population; create accurate instruments through pilot testing and refinement; collect data for statistical processing; and make generalizations about certain factors or variables. Furthermore, the questionnaire as a survey tool allows researchers to collect various types of data suitable for specific studies. It is easy to implement, increases the generalizability of the research findings and allows in-depth statistical analysis (Hair et al., 2019).

Research sampling method

"The research sampling method includes ways of taking a part of the population and using this part as a representation of the entire population" (Acharyya & Bhattacharya, 2020, p. 183). The sampling method can be carried out in one of two main forms: probability sampling and non-probability sampling (Creswell & Guetterman, 2019). This study uses a cluster probability sampling method. Due to the geographical characteristics of Tien Giang province, which is narrow in width but long in length compared to other provinces in the Mekong Delta, schools are distributed according to geographical regions. To conduct the study conveniently and ensure the sample is representative across all regions of Tien Giang province, the author divided the sampling area into five different clusters. Cluster 1 (Go Cong Dong and Tan Phu Dong districts), Cluster 2 (Go Cong town and Go Cong Tay district), Cluster 3 (Cho Gao district and My Tho city), Cluster 4 (Chau Thanh and Cai Lay districts), Cluster 5 (Cai Be and Tan Phuoc districts). To conduct the sample selection, the following steps can be employed:

- Step 1: Create a list of 38 high schools in districts, towns and cities in Tien Giang province.
- Step 2: Group high schools into clusters in which Cluster 1 has 7 schools; Cluster 2 has 8 schools; Cluster 3 has 8 schools; Cluster 4 has 8 schools; and Cluster 5 has 7 schools.
- Step 3: Write each school's name of a cluster into a piece paper, place them in a ballot box, then randomly select two schools in each cluster for the official survey. Consequently, there are 10 out of 38 high schools from the five clusters chosen.

Since the schools selected in each cluster have their different populations, to make sure that the number of participants are large enough for each cluster's representatives, the minimum sample size is calculated. The result is that the population of 10 schools selected is 14,994 students. Cluster 1 has 2314 students (15.43%), Cluster 2 has 3750 students (25.01%), Cluster 3 has 2742 students (18.29%), Cluster 4 has 3166 students (21.12%), and Cluster 5 has 3022 students (20.15%). In fact, the real number of students participated in each cluster can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Number of students at ten selected high schools

Clusters	Selected schools	Grade 10	Grade 11	Grade 12	Total	Total in each cluster	% in each cluster	Minimum size required	Real number participated
1	School 1	569	457	487	1513	2314	15.43	61	357
	School 2	285	260	256	801				120
2	School 3	629	611	611	1851	3750	25.01	99	149
	School 4	663	620	616	1899				68
3	School 5	673	670	658	2001	2742	18.29	73	548
	School 6	266	241	234	741				117
4	School 7	530	481	434	1445	3166	21.12	84	162
	School 8	582	581	558	1721				102
5	School 9	625	612	605	1842	3022	20.15	80	103
	School 10	425	394	361	1180				103
Total		5247	4927	4820	14994	14994	100	397	1829

Research sample size

Sample size is the number of individuals from whom you obtain the necessary information (Kumar et al., 2022). Selecting an appropriate sample size in scientific research is very important. In practice, different studies choose different sample sizes. This depends on many factors such as the type of research design, the sampling method, the size of the parameter studied, the level of discrepancy between the sample parameter and the population one.

To determine the sample size for this study, the author relies on proposals for sample size calculation from the researches of some authors below:

According to Yamane Taro (1973), the determination of the minimum research sample size will be done by using the formula: $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$, where: - n: the required sample size; - N: the size of the research population; - e: the acceptable margin of error. This study chooses ± 0.05 (95%), the most common level.

According to the statistics from Tien Giang Service of Education and Training (2024), the number of administrators, teachers of English and students at 38 high schools in the academic year of 2023-2024 were 132 administrators, 325 teachers of English and 48775 students. Applying the above formula, the minimum sample size with a 5% error rate for administrators and teachers in this study is: $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} = \frac{457}{1+457(0.05)^2} = 213.3022 \approx 213$ (educators). And the minimum sample size with a 5% error rate for students in this study is: $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} = \frac{48775}{1+48775(0.05)^2} = 396.7463 \approx 397$ (students).

Additionally, to determine the sample size for *Exploratory Factor Analysis* (EFA), Kaiser (1974) recommends that the minimum sample size required for the EFA results to be reliable is at least 5 times the number of observed variables. Tabachnick and Fidell (2013) suggest that the minimum sample size should be at least 300 observations for EFA to achieve high accuracy. However, they also note that if factor loadings are strong (0.6 or higher), smaller samples may be acceptable. Hair et al. (2019) find that the minimum sample size for EFA is 50, with 100 or more being preferable. They also agree with previous recommendations that the minimum sample size should be 5 times the number of observed variables.

Thus, the common point of these studies is that a high-reliable sample size for EFA is either 5 times the number of observed variables or a minimum of 100 observations. In this study, the number of observed variables in the questionnaire for administrators and teachers directly participating in the EFA for '*English learning assessment activities; content, methods, forms, and tools of assessment; and factors influencing these activities*' is 99. The number of variables taking part in the EFA for '*The management of students' English learning assessment activities*' is 80. The minimum sample size for EFA in this study must be 100 variables or more (Hair et al., 2019). The real number of participants in the official survey who are eligible for selection (completing the questionnaire) is 418 administrators and teachers of English, which is more than four times the minimum sample size proposed. This fully satisfies the requirements.

For the student questionnaire, the number of variables used for the EFA in '*English learning assessment activities; contents, methods, forms, and tools of assessment; and factors influencing these activities*' is 85. The actual number of students eligible for selection (completing the questionnaire) is 1829, which is more than 18 times the minimum sample size proposed by Hair et al. (2019). Therefore, this sample size fully meets the necessary conditions for participating in EFA in this study.

Research methods

Quantitative research method

Research designs are typically classified into three main groups: quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Asenahabi, 2019; Saliya, 2023). This study adopts a mixed-method approach to achieve its research objectives. Creswell and Creswell (2018) suggest that a mixed-method approach involves a two-phase project: The first phase is to collect and analyze quantitative data and the second one is used for qualitative analysis.

To collect quantitative data, a questionnaire is employed to gather information from the participants (administrators, teachers and students). Its data will be analyzed and processed to understand the current state of students' English learning assessment activities at high schools in Tien Giang province; the management of students' English learning assessment activities; and the factors impacting their management. The questionnaire's contents includes (1) The importance of students' English learning assessment activities at high schools, (2) The importance of managing students' English learning assessment activities, (3) The role of English learning assessment activities in teaching and learning, (4) The level of participation in training courses on English

assessment, (5) The level of application and achievement of English learning assessment activities, (6) The frequency of use of different assessment methods and forms, (7) The frequency of use of various assessment tools, (8) The content of assessment activities, (9) The frequency and effectiveness of managing the preparation for assessment activities using the PDCA approach, (10) The frequency and effectiveness of managing the implementation of assessment activities in the PDCA approach, (11) The frequency and effectiveness of managing the use of assessment results in the PDCA approach, and (12) factors impacting the management of students' English learning assessment activities in the PDCA approach.

Qualitative research method

The in-depth interview, according to Boyce and Neale (2006), is a method used to gather participants' opinions to supplement and clarify the research issues that have not fully been covered by the survey through the questionnaires on the current state of students' English learning assessment activities, the management of these activities, and some factors impacting them. The in-depth interview is conducted on principals from the ten high schools selected in Tien Giang province to understand their perspectives and feelings on research issues. The interview contents in this study mainly focus on the current state of students' English learning assessment activities; the current state of the management of these activities at schools in term of PDCA approach; and the factors influencing the management of students' English learning assessment. This information helps clarify and supplement the quantitative data collected in the official surveys.

Data analysis methods

In this study, the author used SPSS 27.0 to perform quantitative data analysis and processing. The methods included descriptive statistics, linear correlation analysis, regression analysis, analysis of variance, and independent t-tests.

a. *Descriptive statistics*: can be classified by the number of variables involved: variate or multivariate. The simplest way to describe a variable's numerical data is through a frequency distribution (Neuman, 2014). Descriptive statistics were used to determine frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation of variables related to respondents' personal information and their perceptions on the role of management of students' English learning assessment at high schools in Tien Giang province.

b. *Regression analysis*: is a statistical method used to examine the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables (Hair et al., 2019). It can predict the value of a dependent variable based on the value of one or more independent variables through calculating a regression equation (Saunders et al., 2016). In this study, regression analysis is used to explore the relationship between independent variables (related to management subjects, management objects, and influencing factors) and the dependent variable (the management of students' English learning assessment at high schools). This analysis helps determine the strength and direction of these correlations (positive or negative), which informed the development of appropriate solutions to improve the management of students' English learning assessment at high schools in Tien Giang province.

c. *Independent t-test*: According to Hair et al. (2019), an independent t-test is used to compare the mean values of a quantitative variable between two different groups of respondents. In this study, it is used to address the question: Is there a difference in the perception of the management of students' English learning assessment at high schools based on the respondents' positions?

RELIABILITY

Reliability refers to consistency, which often means a measurement instrument or data under specific conditions without distorting the measurement results (Mackey & Gass, 2022). In this study, to measure the reliability of the scale, including the independent and dependent variables, SPSS 27.0 software is employed to run the Cronbach's alpha coefficient for each group of variables. In addition, the *exploratory factor analysis* (EFA) and *the total variance explained* for each group are examined. According to Hair et al. (2019), a highly reliable scale has a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.7 or higher. However, for exploratory research, a Cronbach's alpha threshold of 0.6 is acceptable. The higher the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is, the greater the reliability of the scale becomes. Another key variable in analyzing scale reliability is *the Corrected Item – Total Correlation index*. According to Cristobal et al. (2007) and Hair et al. (2019), a good scale requires observed variables to have a 'Corrected Item – Total Correlation' index of 0.3 or higher. Therefore, to ensure scale reliability, one must rely on two important indices: (1) Cronbach's alpha must be 0.6 or higher (Nunnally, 1978), and (2) the Corrected Item – Total Correlation must be 0.3 or higher. Additionally, according to

Anderson and Gerbing (1988), total variance explained should be taken consideration in examining variables' reliability. They indicated that it must be 50% or higher for the scale to be considered appropriate and acceptable.

RESEARCH RESULTS

In this study, EFA factor loading, total variance explained and Cronbach's alpha are examined for the current state of students' English learning assessment activities, the current state of the management of students' English learning assessment activities, and the factors impacting the management of students' English learning assessment activities. This can be shown in the following sections.

The current state of students' English learning assessment activities at high schools

The role of assessment activities in English teaching and learning at high schools

Table 2 indicates that the values of EFA factor loading in two groups were generally higher than 0.3. They were spreading from 0.78 to 0.90 for the group of administrators, teachers of English and from 0.72 to 0.89 for the group of students. Their total variances explained were 75.26% and 76.35%, which were greater than 50.0%. And their Cronbach's alpha values were higher than 0.7. This proved that the items of two groups were reliable.

Table 2. EFA results for the role of students' English learning assessment activities in teaching and learning

Contents	EFA factor loading		Total variance explained (%)		Cronbach's alpha	
	Admins & Ts	Sts	Admins & Ts	Sts	Admins & Ts	Sts
1.1. Supplying feedback to the teaching process so that teachers can adjust their teaching.	0.90	0.72				
1.2. Supplying feedback to the learning process so that students can adjust their learning.	0.78	0.75				
1.3. Identifying difficulties and limitations of students so that teachers and students can improve their teaching and learning.	0.84	0.78				
1.4. Identifying students' communicative and English linguistic competence.	0.81	0.80				
1.5. Enhancing students' learning motivation.	0.88	0.87				
1.6. Giving feedback on strong and weak points of students' English competence.	0.90	0.88				
1.7. Helping teachers assess students' critical thinking and creativity.	0.85	0.89	75.26	76.35	0.979	0.977
1.8. Developing students' self-learning ability and their confidence in making decisions on their learning goals.	0.79	0.87				
1.9. Helping students participate in self-assessment and peer-assessment.	0.79	0.86				
1.10. Supplying teachers information on students' learning needs.	0.82	0.87				
1.11. Fostering students' participation on their learning process.	0.81	0.88				
1.12. Sharing learning responsibility among students and reducing their worriedness.	0.88	0.88				
1.13. Building close relationship with students and their parents.	0.84	0.86				

1.14. Level of achieving subject objectives and meeting its requirements.	0.87	0.87
1.15. Providing an overall report on students' performance at a particular point of time.	0.79	0.88
1.16. Identifying students' academic achievement/proficiency level.	0.86	0.83
1.17. Helping students see their real performances and set goals for their next learning process.	0.78	0.86
1.18. Accounting English learning results for stakeholders.	0.83	0.83
1.19. Comparing students within a group and ranking their performances	0.81	0.72
1.20. Determining whether students are qualified or not to study at a higher level.	0.89	0.81
1.21. Helping school leaders direct teachers to flexibly use different assessment methods.	0.81	-
1.22. Providing useful information for administrators to shape strategies for improving teaching and learning quality at schools.	0.81	-

In the non-official interview, teacher 1 (T1) expressed, “Assessment activities play an important role in teaching and learning at high schools. They help teachers evaluate students’ real competence of English skills and knowledge”. School leader 2 (L2) stated, “English learning assessment supplies teachers and students feedbacks on their teaching and learning. From that, they adjust their shortcomings.” Thus, it can be said that English learning assessment is a pivotal activity in language teaching and learning at schools.

Training on students’ English learning assessment

The results in Table 3 reveal that the values of EFA factor loading were spreading from 0.71 to 0.81, which was greater than 0.3. Similarly, their total variance explained was at the level of 57.25%, which was higher than 50.0%. Besides, their Cronbach’s alpha (0.812) was higher than 0.7. This confirmed that items in this section are quite reliable.

Through the interview, T3 revealed, “I often take part in some trainings on English learning assessment organized by Vietnam Ministry of Education and Training and by Department of Education and Training. Sometimes, I attend some online trainings at my school. I also have a plan for my self-training and even learn at higher education to improve my profession.” Additionally, L1 confirmed, “Every year, teachers at my school participate in some professional trainings. This makes them more skilful at learning assessment.”

Table 3. EFA results for Training on students’ English learning assessment

Contents	EFA factor loading	Total variance explained (%)	Cronbach’s alpha
2.1. Training held by schools.	0.75	57.27	0.812
2.2. Training organized by Department of Education and Training.	0.81		
2.3. Training held by the Vietnam Ministry of Education and Training.	0.71		
2.4. Training organized by universities or institutions.	0.78		
2.5. Self-training of each individual.	0.73		

Students’ English learning assessment activities at high schools

Data in Table 4 show that EFA factor loadings of two groups in three phases of ‘Preparation for students’ English learning assessment activities, Implementation of students’ English learning assessment activities, Use of students’ English learning results’ were definitely higher than 0.3. They were stretching from 0.70 to 0.97 for group of administrators, teacher and from 0.88 to 0.94 for group of students. Additionally, their total variances explained were greater than 50.0%. Remarkably, their Cronbach’s alphas in three phases were perfect. They were higher than 0.7. This indicates that items of two groups in this section are reliable for conducting the research.

Table 4. EFA results for students’ English learning assessment activities at high schools

Phases	Contents	EFA factor loading		Total variance explained (%)		Cronbach’s alpha	
		Admins & Ts	Sts	Admins & Ts	Sts	Admins & Ts	Sts
Preparation for students’ English learning assessment activities	3.1. Designing an English learning assessment plan (including formative and summative assessment for language skills and knowledge).	0.97	0.90				
	3.2. Designing matrixes and specifications for English tests	0.87	0.92				
	3.3. Designing questions and answer keys/ marking instructions for English tests.	0.89	0.93				
	3.4. Constructing procedures for students’ English learning assessment.	0.90	0.91	81.46	83.12	0.954	0.959
	3.5. Giving professional training on English assessment to administrators and teaching staff according to Ministry of Education and training guides.	0.92	0.91				
	3.6. Preparing equipment, facilities and information technology systems for students’ English learning assessment activities.	0.86	0.91				
	3.7. Organizing the implementation of formative assessment.	0.90	0.89				
Implementation of students’ English learning assessment activities	3.8. Organizing the implementation of summative assessment.	0.84	0.91				
	3.9. Organizing the supervision of students’ English learning assessment.	0.86	0.90	79.68	81.41	0.936	0.943
	3.10. Organizing the arrangement of equipment, facilities, and information technology systems for students’ English learning assessment activities.	0.97	0.88				
	3.11. Organizing feedback collection on students’ English learning assessment to adjust teaching, learning and assessment activities.	0.88	0.93				
Use of students’ English learning results	3.12. Using students’ English learning results after each stage to adjust and improve English teaching and learning activities.	0.70	0.94	79.18	82.67	0.963	0.947
	3.13. Using students’ English learning results after each assessment stage to adjust and improve school policies and strategies.	0.91	-				

3.14. Holding meetings to draw lessons from English learning assessment activities.	0.88	-
3.15. Correcting mid-term and end-term tests to help students identify their weaknesses for their next improvement.	0.91	0.91
3.16. Reporting English learning results to related stakeholders (students, families, etc.).	0.94	0.90
3.17. Providing professional training on English learning assessment for administrators and teaching staff.	0.92	-
3.18. Adjusting and improving assessment activities appropriate with regulations and students' real performances.	0.91	0.91
3.19. Proposing the purchase, supplementation or reparation of facilities for English teaching, learning and assessment activities.	0.93	0.89

In the interview, L3 said, “To conduct students’ learning assessment, we firstly prepare some things for this stage such as building the evaluation plan, designing the matrix, test and its grading guide, distributing equipment, facilities for assessment. Then, we organize the exams, give marks and address the results to related parties.”

English learning assessment methods and forms

The results in Table 5 state that the EFA factor loading of two groups were greater than an acceptable value (0.3). Their total variances explained were 73.22% and 78.10%, which were higher than a normal accepted level (50.0%). The most important thing is that their Cronbach’s alphas were 0.908 and 0.929, which were greater than 0.7, a level for good reliability. Thus, it can be said that items in two groups are reliable.

Besides, in the non-official interview, T3 and T4 emphasized that they used variety of methods and forms in assessing students’ English learning. Some popular methods and forms they used in classrooms were multiple choice test, written test and oral test.”

Table 5. EFA results for English learning assessment methods and forms

<i>Contents</i>	<i>EFA factor loading</i>		<i>Total variance explained (%)</i>		<i>Cronbach’s alpha</i>	
	<i>Admins & Ts</i>	<i>Sts</i>	<i>Admins & Ts</i>	<i>Sts</i>	<i>Admins & Ts</i>	<i>Sts</i>
4.1. Written test	0.87	0.90				
4.2. Multiple-choice test	0.92	0.90				
4.3. Oral test/interview	0.87	0.90	73.22	78.10	0.908	0.929
4.4. Assessment of activity and learning product	0.82	0.84				
4.5. Observation	0.79	0.87				

4.1.5. English learning assessment tools

Data in Table 6 reveal that the values of EFA factor loading in two groups still maintained higher than 0.3. Their total variances explained were at 69.74% and 79.05%, which were greater than 50.0%, an acceptable value. Besides, the Cronbach’s alphas in two groups were 0.927 and 0.954, which higher than 0.7. It can be said that all items in this section satisfy the reliability in the research.

Table 6. EFA results for English learning assessment tools

Contents	EFA factor loading		Total variance explained (%)		Cronbach's alpha	
	Admins & Ts	Sts	Admins & Ts	Sts	Admins & Ts	Sts
5.1. Checklists for assessing presentations, essays, and learning products.	0.86	0.84				
5.2. Scales for assessing the proficiency level of essays, learning products, and presentations.	0.84	0.83				
5.3. Rubrics for assessing the four language skills, learning projects and learning products.	0.75	0.89				
5.4. Portfolios for assessing students' learning products during a semester/academic year.	0.91	0.91				
5.5. Project-based learning for assessing project completion, each member contributions, and the effectiveness of the learning project.	0.75	0.92	69.74	79.05	0.927	0.954
5.6. Peer assessment to evaluate students' performances by relying on criteria and marking guides provided by the teacher.	0.87	0.91				
5.7. Self-assessment to evaluate students' own learning products by basing on criteria set by the teacher.	0.84	0.91				

The contents of students' English learning assessment activities

Table 7 indicates that the values of EFA factor loading in two groups had a positive tendency. They all were greater than 0.3, a minimum acceptable level in the study. In addition, their total variances explained achieved at 81.99% and 81.48%, which were higher than 50.0%, a necessary value for good items. Especially, their Cronbach's alphas gained at 0.983 and 0.982, which meet the requirement of high reliability in these formal surveys.

Table 7. EFA results for the contents of students' English learning assessment activities

Contents	EFA factor loading		Total variance explained (%)		Cronbach's alpha	
	Admins & Ts	Sts	Admins & Ts	Sts	Admins & Ts	Sts
6.1. The contents of formative assessment include core knowledge of each unit, key themes and topics from the 2018 General Education Program.	0.93	0.92				
6.2. Formative assessment focuses on the four skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing as well as language knowledge.	0.90	0.92	81.99	81.48	0.983	0.982
6.3. Questions in formative assessment tests are stretching from easy to difficult, covering three levels of recognition, comprehension and application.	0.89	0.89				

6.4. The contents of formative assessment tests are based on the required knowledge and language skills for each grade.	0.93	0.91
6.5. The contents of formative assessment tests are closely connected to the learning program.	0.89	0.87
6.6. The contents of summative assessment tests are designed by basing on the requirements of learning goals and achievements of each grade.	0.87	0.88
6.7. Questions of summative assessment tests are spreading from easy to difficult with three levels of recognition, comprehension, and application.	0.93	0.91
6.8. The structure of summative assessment tests is closely based on the agreed-upon matrix and the learning program.	0.90	0.93
6.9. Summative assessment tests evaluate four skills of listening, speaking, reading, writing, and language knowledge.	0.89	0.90
6.10. Summative assessment tests have to ensure accuracy, scientific rigor, and high confidentiality.	0.93	0.91
6.11. Summative assessment tests are organized simultaneously for each grade.	0.89	0.87
6.12. The supervision for summative assessment is conducted seriously and strictly.	0.88	0.88
6.13. The scoring of summative assessment tests is objective and fair, basing on the marking instructions.	0.93	0.91
6.14. The correction and returning of tests are done after the teacher has finished scoring for all students.	0.92	0.93

Through the non-official interview, T1 exposed, “Testing students is purposeful. The contents of tests I gave students focus on main points in each unit and base on themes or topics in the current program. Remarkably, they meet requirements on language skills and knowledge.”

The current state of management of students’ English learning assessment activities at high schools

The management of the preparation for students’ English learning assessment activities at high schools

The results in Table 8 show that the values EFA of factor loading in four phases were spreading from 0.76 to 0.96, which were much higher than 0.3, a minimum accepted value for remaining items. Another important values of four phases were *total variances explained*, which were greater than 50.0%. Interestingly, their Cronbach’s alphas were stretching from 0.861 to 0.964. This strongly confirmed that items in each group had high reliability and met requirements in this research.

Table 8. EFA results for the management of the preparation for students' English learning assessment activities

Phases	Contents	EFA factor loading	Total variance explained (%)	Cronbach's alpha
Plan	7.1. Planning the construction of the summative assessment design for the academic year.	0.76	64.57	0.861
	7.2. Planning the matrix design and test specifications for mid-term tests.	0.80		
	7.3. Planning the matrix design and test specifications for end-term tests.	0.84		
	7.4. Planning the assignment of designing questions and marking guides/ assessment criteria for mid-term tests.	0.81		
	7.5. Planning the assignment of designing questions and marking guides/ assessment criteria for end-term tests.	0.80		
Do	7.6. Implementing the construction of the summative assessment plan for the academic year.	0.76	77.16	0.920
	7.7. Implementing the construction of the matrixes and specifications for mid-term tests.	0.91		
	7.8. Implementing the construction of the matrixes and specifications for end-term tests.	0.90		
	7.9. Implementing the assignment of designing questions and marking guides/assessment criteria for mid-term tests.	0.93		
	7.10. Implementing the assignment of designing questions and marking guides/assessment criteria for end-term tests.	0.88		
Check	7.11. Checking the summative assessment plan for the academic year.	0.96	86.46	0.960
	7.12. Checking the matrixes and specifications for mid-term tests.	0.93		
	7.13. Checking the matrixes and specifications for end-term tests.	0.93		
	7.14. Checking and approving questions and marking guides/assessment criteria for mid-term tests.	0.95		
	7.15. Checking and approving questions and marking guides/assessment criteria for end-term tests.	0.87		
Act	7.16. Improving the summative assessment plan for each academic year.	0.92	87.94	0.964
	7.17. Improving the matrixes and specifications for mid-term tests.	0.91		
	7.18. Improving the matrix and specifications for end-term tests.	0.95		
	7.19. Improving the questions and marking guides/assessment criteria for mid-term tests.	0.96		
	7.20. Improving the questions and marking guides/assessment criteria for end-term tests.	0.95		

Management of the implementation of students' English learning assessment activities at high schools

Table 9 remarks that the values of EFA factor loading for the management of the implementation of students' English learning assessment activities in four phases were achieving from 0.72 to 0.95. They were much higher than 0.3, a minimum accepted level for sustaining items in their group. Besides, the total variances explained in phases of *Plan, Do, Check, Act* were 78.27%, 64.78%, 71.35% and 76.77%, accordingly. These percentages were greater than 50.0%, an acceptable value in this study. Similarly, their Cronbach's alphas were much higher than 0.7. Thus, it can be said that items in this section are reliable.

Table 9. EFA results for the management of the implementation of students' English learning assessment activities

Phases	Contents	EFA factor loading	Total variance explained (%)	Cronbach's alpha
Plan	8.1. Planning the organization of printing, copying, securing and storing summative assessment tests appropriately with school regulations.	0.95	78.27	0.959
	8.2. Planning the organization of arranging exam rooms, test schedules, student lists, examiner lists, supervisor lists, and support staff lists for summative assessment tests.	0.88		
	8.3. Planning the organization of invigilation for summative assessment tests.	0.83		
	8.4. Planning the organization of supervision for summative assessment tests.	0.90		
	8.5. Planning the organization of scoring summative assessment tests.	0.92		
	8.6. Planning the organization of rescoring tests upon student request.	0.82		
	8.7. Planning the arrangement of equipment, facilities and information technology systems for students' English learning assessment activities.	0.92		
	8.8. Planning the organization of collecting student feedback on their English learning assessment to adjust teaching, learning and assessment activities.	0.85		
Do	8.9. Organizing the printing, copying, securing and storing of summative assessment tests appropriately with school regulations.	0.81	64.78	0.921
	8.10. Organizing the arrangement of exam rooms, schedules, student lists, examiner lists, supervisor lists and support staff lists for summative assessment tests.	0.88		
	8.11. Organizing invigilation for summative assessment tests.	0.80		
	8.12. Organizing supervision for summative assessment tests.	0.85		
	8.13. Organizing the scoring of summative assessment tests.	0.82		
	8.14. Organizing the rescoring of tests upon student request.	0.79		
	8.15. Arranging equipment, facilities, and information technology systems to serve students' English learning assessment activities.	0.76		

	8.16. Implementing the collection of student feedback on their English learning assessment to adjust teaching, learning and assessment activities.	0.72		
Check	8.17. Checking the organization of printing, copying, securing, and storing summative assessment tests appropriately with school regulations.	0.77		
	8.18. Checking the organization of arranging exam rooms, schedules, student lists, examiner lists, supervisor lists and support staff lists for summative assessment tests.	0.82		
	8.19. Checking the organization of invigilation for summative assessment tests.	0.88		
	8.20. Checking the organization of supervision for summative assessment tests.	0.95		
	8.21. Checking the organization of scoring summative assessment tests.	0.88	71.35	0.940
	8.22. Checking the organization of rescoring tests upon student request.	0.87		
	8.23. Checking the arrangement of equipment, facilities and information technology systems for students' English learning assessment activities.	0.84		
	8.24. Checking the collection of student feedback on their English learning assessment to adjust teaching, learning and assessment activities.	0.74		
Act	8.25. Improving the organization of printing, copying, securing and storing summative assessment tests appropriately with school regulations.	0.89		
	8.26. Improving the organization of arranging exam rooms, schedules, student lists, examiner lists, supervisor lists and support staff lists for summative assessment tests.	0.86		
	8.27. Improving the organization of invigilation for summative assessment tests.	0.88		
	8.28. Improving the organization of supervision for summative assessment tests.	0.89		
	8.29. Improving the organization of scoring summative assessment tests.	0.88	76.77	0.955
	8.30. Improving the organization of rescoring tests upon student request.	0.87		
	8.31. Improving the arrangement of equipment, facilities and information technology systems for students' English learning assessment activities.	0.86		
	8.32. Improving the collection of student feedback on their English learning assessment to adjust teaching, learning and assessment activities.	0.89		

Management of the use of students' English assessment results at high schools

Data in Table 10 state that the values of EFA factor loading in managing the use of students' English assessment activities were stretching from 0.78 to 0.98. They were much higher than an accepted level (0.3). Additionally, the total variances explained

in four phases were much greater than 50.0%. Especially, their Cronbach’s alphas were quite higher than 0.7. This proves that items in these phases are suitable and reliable for this research.

Table 10. EFA results for the management of the use of students’ English assessment activities

Phases	Contents	EFA factor loading	Total variance explained (%)	Cronbach’s alpha
Plan	9.1. Planning the analysis of assessment results/score distribution after each assessment stage to adjust teaching and learning activities as well as support learners.	0.98	82.09	0.963
	9.2. Planning the organization of the teaching staff meetings to draw lessons from students’ English learning assessment activities.	0.90		
	9.3. Planning the correction of summative assessment tests for students and indicating their weaknesses.	0.93		
	9.4. Planning the organization of the weak students’ parent meetings to discuss some measures supporting them.	0.78		
	9.5. Planning professional development and training on assessment for the school administrators and teaching staff.	0.92		
	9.6. Planning the adjustment and improvement of school policies and strategies.	0.93		
	9.7. Planning the purchase, supplementation or repair of facilities for English teaching, learning and assessment activities.	0.90		
Do	9.8. Analyzing assessment results, score distribution after each assessment stage to draw lessons for adjusting teaching and learning activities as well as supporting learners.	0.93	79.13	0.955
	9.9. Organizing the teaching staff meetings to draw lessons on students’ English learning assessment activities.	0.92		
	9.10. Organizing the correction of summative assessment tests for students, indicating their weaknesses.	0.95		
	9.11. Organizing the weak students’ parent meetings to discuss some measures supporting them.	0.72		
	9.12. Organizing professional development and training on assessment for the school administrators and teaching staff.	0.98		
	9.13. Organizing the adjustment and improvement of school policies and strategies.	0.86		
	9.14. Organizing the purchase, supplementation or repair of facilities for English teaching, learning and assessment activities.	0.83		
Check	9.15. Checking the analysis of assessment results, score distribution after each assessment stage to draw lessons for adjusting teaching, learning activities and supporting learners.	0.94	80.09	0.958
	9.16. Checking the organization of the teaching staff meetings to draw lessons on students’ English learning assessment activities.	0.91		

	9.17. Checking the organization of correcting summative assessment tests for students, indicating their weaknesses.	0.83		
	9.18. Checking the organization of the weak students' parent meetings to discuss some measures supporting them.	0.87		
	9.19. Checking the professional development and training on assessment for the school administrators and teaching staff.	0.92		
	9.20. Checking the adjustment and improvement of school policies and strategies.	0.97		
	9.21. Checking the purchase, supplementation, repair of facilities for English teaching, learning and assessment activities.	0.81		
	9.22. Improving the analysis of assessment results, score distribution after each assessment stage to draw lessons for adjusting teaching, learning activities and supporting learners.	0.98		
	9.23. Improving the organization of the teaching staff meetings to draw lessons on students' English learning assessment activities.	0.88		
	9.24. Improving the organization of correcting summative assessment tests for students, indicating their weaknesses.	0.98		
Act	9.25. Improving the organization of the weak students' parent meetings to discuss some measures supporting them.	0.91	81.03	0.960
	9.26. Improving the professional development and training on assessment for the school administrators and teaching staff.	0.78		
	9.27. Improving the adjustment and improvement of school policies and strategies.	0.94		
	9.28. Improving the purchase, supplementation, repair of facilities for English teaching, learning and assessment activities.	0.82		

Factors influencing the management of students' English learning assessment activities at high schools

The results in Table 11 reveal that the values of EFA factor loading in both groups were wonderful. They were higher than 0.3, an acceptable level for keeping items in a group. In addition, their total variances explained were quite greater than 50.0%, a level to ensure items having interactions within their groups. Noticeably, their Cronbach's alphas were completely higher than 0.7, a value to make sure a group of items having high reliability. Therefore, it can be said that items in two groups are good and reliable for conducting the surveys.

Table 11. EFA results for factors influencing the management of students' English learning assessment activities

Factors	Contents	EFA factor loading		Total variance explained (%)		Cronbach's alpha	
		Admins & Ts	Sts	Admins & Ts	Sts	Admins & Ts	Sts
Awareness of administrators, teachers and students on learners'	10.1. Administrators' awareness on students' English learning assessment.	0.92	-	78.17	85.53	0.925	0.915
	10.2. Administrators' awareness of their leadership roles in students' English learning assessment.	0.87	-				

English learning assessment	10.3. The responsibility spirit of administrators, teachers and students on learners' English learning assessment activities.	0.96	0.93				
	10.4. The attitude of administrators, teachers and students towards learners' English learning assessment activities.	0.83	0.92				
	10.5. Students' learning consciousness (motivation and learning goals) toward English learning assessment activities at high schools.	0.84	0.92				
Competences of administrators, teachers and students	10.6. The management and leadership competences of administrators on students' English learning assessment activities.	0.88	0.93				
	10.7. The competency of teachers in students' English learning assessment (professional/ pedagogical qualifications, teaching methods).	0.92	0.95	77.47	87.83	0.902	0.954
	10.8. The competency of students in their English learning assessment (knowledge, test-taking skills).	0.82	0.94				
	10.9. The understanding of administrators, teachers and students on regulations of assessment activities.	0.90	0.92				
Physical condition and equipment	10.10. The physical condition and equipment necessary for students' learning assessment (classrooms, desks, chairs, projectors, sound systems, lighting, fans, etc.).	0.92	0.88				
	10.11. Learning resources and teaching aids in the library and equipment room meeting subject/ course requirements.	0.77	0.93	75.23	82.57	0.835	0.894
	10.12. The information technology system serving teaching, learning and students' English learning assessment activities.	0.90	0.92				
Teaching and learning environment	10.13. The relationship between teachers and students (respectful, friendly, sociable, helpful).	0.78	0.87				
	10.14. The relationship among students.	0.85	0.90				
	10.15. The teaching and learning space for teachers and students (clean, spacious, quiet).	0.96	0.89	68.82	77.04	0.887	0.925
	10.16. Healthy competition in learning among students.	0.87	0.84				

	10.17. The supports from the school administrators and relevant stakeholders in teaching and learning processes for teachers and students.	0.67	0.89				
	10.18. Directives on implementing the assessment and ranking of students' English learning results at high schools.	0.96	0.86				
	10.19. Requirements on contents and learning outcomes for English learning assessment at high schools.	0.96	0.88				
Policies and legal regulations on foreign languages	10.20. Regulations on the learning duration and test-taking time for English tests at high schools.	0.92	0.88	84.69	76.06	0.953	0.921
	10.21. Regulations on the methods, forms, and tools for students' English learning assessment activities at high schools.	0.91	0.89				
	10.22. Policies on resource investment for training, professional development, teaching-learning, and English learning assessment at the high schools.	0.85	0.85				
	10.23. Attention, encouragement and investment from students' families.	0.88	0.92				
Family and society	10.24. Attention and support from the community, local authorities for poor students.	0.91	0.87	78.89	78.39	0.866	0.860
	10.25. The awareness of students' families, society on students' academic achievements.	0.88	0.87				

To sum up, the items in three sections on (1) the current state of students' English learning assessment activities, (2) the current state of the management of students' English learning assessment activities, and (3) the factors influencing the management of students' English learning assessment activities at high schools, demonstrate good quality of item clusters as their Cronbach's alphas are higher than 0.7. Besides, their EFA factors loading are greater than 0.3 and their total variances explained are higher than 50.0%. This clearly explicits that the items in questionnaires for administrators, teachers of English and students achieve high reliability in this research.

CONCLUSION

This study conducted *'The research design on the management of students' English learning assessment activities at high schools in Tien Giang province, Vietnam'* in the PDCA approach. It employed a mixed method through questionnaires and in-depth interviews to collect information on (1) The current state of students' English learning assessment activities at high schools, (2) The current state of management of students' English learning assessment activities at high schools, (3) Factors impacting the management of students' English learning assessment activities at high schools. The results indicated that their EFA factor loading values were much greater than 0.3; their total variance explained values were higher than 50.0%; and their Cronbach's alphas were greater than 0.7. This confirmed that items in two groups were reliable for doing the research.

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